

Laying the Groundwork for Bioeconomy Development: Insights from the Strumica Region

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the progress achieved under two research and development projects, BE-Rural and SCALE-UP, in advancing a sustainable bioeconomy in the Municipality of Strumica, North Macedonia, highlighting the transition from strategic planning to concrete implementation. BE-Rural initiated the process by formulating a participatory roadmap structured around six pillars: (1) business development, (2) research and innovation, (3) financing, (4) policy alignment, (5) education and awareness, and (6) international collaboration. Building on this foundation, the Horizon Europe project SCALE-UP supported local bioeconomy development through activities such as biomass potential mapping, identification of bioeconomy-relevant businesses and business models, innovation screening,

targeted trainings, study visits, stakeholder exchanges, and organization of a student competition "Bioeconomy through Art." A key achievement was the creation of Strumica's Bioeconomy Platform within the Environmental Sector of the Municipality Administration serving as a hub for coordination and innovation support.

SCALE-UP's detailed mapping of biomass streams, particularly agricultural residues and organic waste, informed valorisation pathways such as composting and biogas production, tailored to the local agricultural context. While the overall implementation of the Bioeconomy Roadmap is assessed as moderate progress, notable achievements were made in enhancing public sector leadership, community awareness, and initial innovation support. Importantly, bioeconomy activities demonstrated good alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). Persistent challenges include limited private sector engagement, underdeveloped financing flows, language barriers, and declining participation due to repetitive trainings.

To move from moderate to substantial progress, the paper recommends embedding bioeconomy objectives into Strumica's local development strategies, incentivizing innovation, improving access to rural development and innovation funds, and aligning local efforts with European Union instruments such as the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, IPARD, and Horizon Europe. Continued technical support, digital business tools, and a multi-level coordination framework are key to unlocking Strumica's full bioeconomic potential and offering a scalable model for similar regions.

KEYWORDS: Bioeconomy, biomass, circular economy, sustainable development, roadmap, BE-Rural, SCALE-UP, Strumica.

INTRODUCTION

The transition to a circular bioeconomy has emerged as a key strategy for promoting environmental, economic, and social resilience in the face of global sustainability challenges [1] [2]. Growing scientific interest is reflected in a significant increase in related publications, with 385 publications from 50 countries recorded between 2015 and 2021 [3]. Despite this momentum, critical barriers persist, including insufficient assessments of sustainability risks, limited stakeholder engagement, and weak cross-sectoral cooperation [3] [4].

Furthermore, the focus of most bioeconomy studies remains predominantly technical and environmental, with relatively little attention paid to social dimensions, particularly the contributions of bioeconomy strategies to social Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as education, poverty reduction, and gender equality [3] [5] [6]. This gap highlights the need for a broader, more integrated perspective on bioeconomy development.

Research has so far focused largely on Europe and Asia, with a critical underrepresentation of studies examining bioeconomy opportunities in developing and transition economies [5] [7] [8]. In south-eastern and eastern Europe, countries often possess abundant biological resources and strong agricultural traditions but lag behind in innovation capacity, technology deployment, and knowledge-based bioeconomy development [9] [10]. There is thus an urgent need for localized studies that account for specific regional strengths, challenges, and socio-economic contexts.

North Macedonia, an EU candidate country, faces the dual challenge of aligning its development path with European Green Deal priorities and the updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy [11], while also overcoming domestic limitations such as fragmented policies, insufficient stakeholder engagement, and limited support for research and innovation. Although the country has a strong agricultural sector and diverse biological resources, it currently lacks a dedicated national bioeconomy strategy, and its innovation performance remains modest compared to EU averages [10] [12].

Recent EU-funded initiatives have begun addressing these challenges. The BE-Rural project promoted participatory development of bioeconomy strategies in rural regions, including the Municipality of Strumica, where a Bioeconomy Roadmap was produced in 2021 [13]. Building on this foundation, the ongoing SCALE-UP project seeks to support the implementation of bioeconomy actions through capacity-building, biomass potential mapping, business model development, and stakeholder engagement in North Macedonia and other partner regions [14] [15].

This paper evaluates the early implementation of the Strumica Bioeconomy Roadmap, assessing achievements across its strategic pillars and its contributions to selected SDGs. By focusing on a rural region within an EU accession country, the study aims to contribute to a better understanding of how bioeconomy development can foster resilience, innovation, and inclusivity in transitioning economies, offering insights relevant to both regional policymakers and broader EU bioeconomy ambitions.

METHODS

This study applied a structured, evidence-based methodology based on a comprehensive desk review of key strategic and planning documents relevant to the bioeconomy transition in the Municipality of Strumica. The documents analyzed included the Bioeconomy Roadmap for the Strumica Region, publications from the BE-Rural and SCALE-UP projects, as well as other official documents adopted by the Municipality, such as the Local Environmental Action Plan (LEAP) and the Waste Management Plan. Together, these sources provided a detailed basis for understanding the planning, progress, and implementation of bioeconomy-related actions at the regional level.

The analysis centered on the six pillars outlined in the Bioeconomy Roadmap. Each pillar was systematically evaluated to assess its implementation status, effectiveness, and contribution to regional sustainability objectives. The evaluation process involved the identification of strengths and weaknesses for each pillar, followed by a comprehensive synthesis of findings to highlight the overall impact, achievements, and remaining challenges. To ensure a transparent and consistent assessment, a numerical grading scale was employed, defined in Table 1.

In addition to evaluating the implementation of the bioeconomy development roadmap, the contribution of each pillar to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was analysed, focusing on both direct and indirect impacts. This integrative approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the bioeconomy transition's progress in the Strumica region.

To assess the contribution of the bioeconomy development pillars to the SDGs, each pillar was evaluated based on its impact on specific SDGs. Pillars demonstrating a direct impact on a SDG were assigned a score of 2, while those showing an indirect contribution were assigned a score of 1. A score of 0 indicated no contribution to the respective SDG. The goal of this assessment was to quantify how well the bioeconomy development roadmap aligns with global sustainability targets. The resulting SDG matrix provides a clear overview of these contributions, highlighting synergies and identifying areas where further alignment could enhance the region's contribution to sustainable development.

Table 1: Grading scale for progress assessment

Grade	Definition
5	Excellent progress: Full implementation with significant, measurable outcomes; strategic strengths clearly outweigh any minor weaknesses.
4	Good progress: Substantial implementation with effective outcomes; strengths are evident, though some moderate weaknesses or improvement opportunities remain.
3	Moderate progress: Partial implementation leading to initial results; a balanced presence of strengths and weaknesses with several critical gaps.
2	Limited progress: Minimal implementation; few achievements overshadowed by major weaknesses hindering overall effectiveness.
1	Very limited progress: Actions largely remain at the planning stage or are poorly executed, yielding negligible results.
0	No progress: No visible implementation efforts; actions are absent or entirely ineffective.

The applied methodology builds on established practices for regional sustainability assessments and was previously validated through its successful application in the Resilient Skopje – Climate Change Strategy for the City of Skopje [16]. In that context, the methodology proved effective in structuring evidence-based assessments of complex regional strategies, reinforcing its applicability and robustness for evaluating the implementation of the Bioeconomy Roadmap in Strumica.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessment of Bioeconomy Development

The Strumica Bioeconomy Development Roadmap contains the following six key pillars: (1) Business Sector Development, (2) Use of Diverse Funding Streams, (3) Research and Innovation Activities, (4) Education and Information, (5) Synergies with Other Policy Fields, and (6) International Collaboration.

The Business Sector Development pillar focuses on fostering growth of bio-based enterprises, particularly in rural areas, through financial incentives, demonstration projects, and youth engagement initiatives.

The Research and Innovation Activities pillar aims to strengthen regional innovation capacities and promote technology adoption by establishing a Knowledge and Innovation System to connect stakeholders and facilitate access to new technologies.

The Use of Diverse Funding Streams pillar highlights the importance of leveraging EU, national, and regional programs, enhancing stakeholders' understanding of financing opportunities, and supporting small businesses in accessing available funds.

The Synergies with Other Policy Fields pillar emphasizes the need for bioeconomy strategies to be integrated with agriculture, energy, and manufacturing policies, aligned with EU regulations and smart specialization strategies.

The Education and Information pillar seeks to promote sustainability by integrating bioeconomy topics into education systems, fostering knowledge-sharing platforms, and running public information campaigns to raise awareness among farmers, youth, and other key groups.

The International Collaboration pillar focuses on building connections with international networks to exchange best practices, access markets, and foster joint innovation initiatives.

Following this overview, an assessment of the development status of each pillar was conducted using the 0–5 grading scale described in the Methods section. The results are summarized in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Summary of the assessment of implementation of Strumica Bioeconomy Development Roadmap

Pillar	Strengths	Weaknesses	Grade (0–5)
1. Business Sector Development	Strong engagement with SMEs and entrepreneurs through the SCALE-UP platform; successful piloting of business models; capacity-building through the Innovation Support Programme; establishment of a Regional Platform for bioeconomy promotion.	Lack of large-scale investments; limited SME financing and scaling support; limited participation from farmers and agro-industries; language barriers reduce access to innovation.	3 Moderate progress
2. Research and Innovation Capacities and Activities	Strong knowledge transfer and practical training; partnerships with universities; pilot projects on composting and biomass valorization; visibility through publications; biopotential mapping activities.	Limited presence of high-level R&D institutions; need for stronger business-research coordination; early stage in compost quality control research; scaling of pilots remains challenging.	3 Moderate progress
3. Use of Diverse EU, National, and Regional Funding Streams	Active linking to EU funding (Horizon Europe, IPA, WeBSEFF); structured technical support through SCALE-UP; good alignment of local plans with EU programs.	Tailored financial tools for early-stage innovators lacking; SMEs face challenges in accessing available funds; rural innovators particularly disadvantaged.	2 Limited progress
4. Synergies with Other Policy Fields	Strong alignment with circular economy, agriculture, energy, and rural development policies; cross-sector collaboration embedded into local strategies (LEAP, Waste Management Plan).	Institutional engagement in agro-industry biomass initiatives still weak; early-stage implementation of monitoring systems; compost quality certification under development.	3 Moderate progress

5. Education and Information in Relation to Sustainability	High stakeholder participation (>30 trained participants from different stakeholder groups); strong youth engagement; highly impactful student competition “Bioeconomy through Art”; effective media outreach and regular information sharing (e.g., biomass mapping).	Limited formal integration into school curricula; rural awareness remains lower; need for greater diversity in training participation; over-reliance on events rather than structured learning pathways.	4 Good progress
6. International Collaboration and Sharing Good Practices	Knowledge-sharing through study tours and field trips; connections to European networks via SCALE-UP; development of flexible meta-cluster models.	Inconsistent follow-up with international partners; language barriers; lack of formal mechanisms for sustaining partnerships post-project.	3 Moderate progress

The assessment of the implementation of the Strumica Bioeconomy Development Roadmap shows moderate overall progress across the six pillars, with important achievements in key areas but significant gaps remaining.

Pillars such as Business Sector Development and Research and Innovation Capacities and Activities demonstrated solid advances, particularly through knowledge transfer activities, SME engagement, and pilot project implementation. However, challenges persist in scaling up innovations and ensuring broader participation from critical sectors such as farming and agro-industries.

The Use of Diverse Funding Streams pillar showed only initial progress, primarily due to limited tailored financial instruments and barriers faced by SMEs and rural innovators in accessing available funding opportunities. Conversely, strong efforts have been made in Education and Information, where a high number of stakeholders were trained, and student competition, youth and media outreach activities were notably successful, despite gaps in formal educational integration.

Efforts toward Synergies with Other Policy Fields and International Collaboration are on track, with clear policy alignment and knowledge-sharing initiatives underway. Yet, the sustainability of partnerships and full operationalization of cross-sector cooperation mechanisms will require further attention.

Overall, the results highlight that the foundations for a regional bioeconomy in Strumica have been established, supported by strong multi-actor engagement and increased awareness. Future efforts should prioritize enhancing financial support mechanisms, scaling pilot initiatives, fostering institutional collaboration, and building formal educational and monitoring structures to sustain momentum and close remaining gaps.

Contribution to Sustainable Development Agenda

In addition to analyzing the direct bioeconomy development outcomes, it is also crucial to assess how these developments contribute to achieving the broader objectives of sustainable development. This section evaluates the alignment of the Strumica Bioeconomy Development Roadmap with key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), highlighting the role of each of

the six identified pillars in driving progress across the SDG agenda. Through a systematic analysis, the contribution of each pillar to the global sustainability framework was examined, considering both direct and indirect impacts. The assessment demonstrates that the bioeconomy initiatives are interconnected with a broad set of sustainable development objectives, enhancing their long-term relevance and impact.

Specifically, Business Sector Development directly supports SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) by fostering entrepreneurship, SME growth, and local value chains, while promoting sustainable practices aligned with SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). Indirectly, it contributes to SDG 1 (No Poverty) through job creation, SDG 13 (Climate Action) by promoting circular bio-based solutions, and SDG 15 (Life on Land) through sustainable land management.

Research & Innovation capacities and activities play a crucial role in directly advancing SDG 9 (Innovation and Infrastructure) and SDG 4 (Quality Education), particularly through university partnerships, hands-on student engagement, and applied research. This pillar also promotes SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) by developing technologies for better biomass use. Indirectly, it enhances SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) through innovations in sustainable agriculture, SDG 13 (Climate Action) via eco-innovations, and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) by fostering collaborative networks.

Use of Diverse Funding Streams directly contributes to SDG 8 and SDG 9 by securing financial mechanisms to scale bio-based innovations. Indirectly, it supports SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) by making funds accessible to rural innovators, and SDG 12 by promoting circular economy projects through financial incentives.

Synergies with Other Policy Fields show strong direct contributions to SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action). The alignment of bioeconomy objectives with rural development, energy, waste management, and climate policies has created multiple positive spillovers. Indirectly, this pillar advances SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 15 (Life on Land) through integrated approaches to resource efficiency.

Education & Information in Relation to Sustainability pillar directly drives SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 12 by raising public awareness and skills in bio-based practices. Its indirect impact stretches to SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) through youth and rural engagement, and SDG 13 (Climate Action) by fostering behavior change towards climate resilience.

Finally, International Collaboration and sharing good practices directly supports SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) by linking Strumica with international knowledge platforms and regional partners. Indirectly, it enhances SDG 9 through the sharing of innovative technologies, SDG 4 by transferring educational content, and SDG 12 by spreading best practices for sustainable production and consumption.

The resulting SDG matrix is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 SDG Matrix: Contribution of Bioeconomy Development Pillars to the Sustainable Development Goals

SDG → Pillar (grade) ↓	1 NO POVERTY	2 ZERO HUNGER	4 QUALITY EDUCATION	5 GENDER EQUALITY	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION	7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES
Business Sector Development (3)	1						2	2	
Research & Innovation (3)		1	2					2	
Use of Funding Streams (2)							2	2	1
Synergies with Policy Fields (3)		2			2	1			
Education & Information (4)			2	1			1		
International Collaboration (3)			1					1	

SDG → Pillar (grade) ↓	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	13 CLIMATE ACTION	15 LIFE ON LAND	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS	Σ	With current progress assessment	With excellent progress
Business Sector Development (3)		2	1	1		9	27	45
Research & Innovation (3)		2	1		1	9	27	45
Use of Funding Streams (2)	1	1				7	14	35
Synergies with Policy Fields (3)	1	2	2	1		11	33	55
Education & Information (4)		2	1			7	28	35
International Collaboration (3)		1			2	5	15	25
Total contribution							144	240

To better understand the current progress, it is useful to compare the results with a hypothetical scenario where all pillars were rated at the maximum score of 5. This scenario represents the optimal contribution of each pillar to the SDG agenda. If all pillars had been assessed with a score of 5, the total contribution across all SDGs would amount to 240. In contrast, the current cumulative SDG score is 144, representing 60% of the optimal contribution.

Overall, the bioeconomy development in the Strumica region—driven largely by the BE-Rural and SCALE-UP projects—has significantly contributed to advancing a wide range of SDGs, demonstrating the potential of localized bioeconomy strategies to support sustainable regional growth. These updated SDG linkages differ slightly from those outlined in the original Bioeconomy Roadmap, as they reflect a deeper and more current assessment informed by new findings, results, and recommendations from the SCALE-UP project, as well as policy developments that have occurred since the Roadmap’s creation in 2021. Among the SDGs, the Bioeconomy Roadmap contributes most strongly to SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), emphasizing the need for sustainable production and consumption practices, particularly through circular economy approaches and bio-based innovations.

While the contribution to economic and environmental goals is notable, the assessment also reveals gaps in addressing social SDGs such as Quality Education (SDG 4), No Poverty (SDG 1), and Gender Equality (SDG 5) - an issue already identified by the scientific community [3]. This updated evaluation provides additional insights into the Roadmap's alignment with these social dimensions, highlighting areas requiring further attention.

For example, although SDG 4 (Quality Education) is indirectly supported through capacity-building activities, student engagement and knowledge exchange initiatives, there remains a lack of targeted, formal education frameworks that integrate bioeconomy concepts into mainstream curricula. The reliance on project-based training and competitions may not suffice to create a lasting, systemic impact, particularly in rural areas where educational opportunities are often limited.

Similarly, SDG 1 (No Poverty) benefits indirectly from job creation and innovation-driven local economic development. However, the absence of specific poverty alleviation measures within the bioeconomy strategy suggests that more deliberate actions are needed to ensure the benefits are inclusive, particularly for vulnerable populations. Tailored support mechanisms, such as targeted funding for low-income communities and rural entrepreneurs, could strengthen the Roadmap's impact on poverty reduction.

Regarding SDG 5 (Gender Equality), while bioeconomy initiatives provide indirect support by creating opportunities for youth and local innovators, explicit gender-focused strategies are largely absent. Greater efforts to promote women's leadership, participation in innovation ecosystems, and inclusion in decision-making processes could significantly enhance the contribution of the bioeconomy agenda to gender equality.

In summary, while the Bioeconomy Roadmap makes a substantial contribution to several key SDGs, particularly those linked to environmental sustainability and economic development, there remains a need to more fully integrate social inclusion and equity considerations. Future strategies could focus on expanding formal educational initiatives, embedding poverty-reduction programs within bio-based business models, and advancing gender-responsive actions to ensure that bioeconomy-driven growth is truly sustainable and inclusive.

Strategic Recommendations for Advancing Bioeconomy Development and SDG Integration

Building on the assessment results and identifying areas for further improvement, the following strategic recommendations are structured according to the pillars of the Strumica Bioeconomy Roadmap. These recommendations aim to accelerate bioeconomy development and strengthen its alignment with the SDGs.

PILLAR 1: Business Sector Development

- Establish regional business support hubs focused on the bioeconomy to help SMEs navigate funding, scaling, certification, and market integration, thereby strengthening the ecosystem for bio-based startups and entrepreneurs.
- Offer seed grants, innovation vouchers, and micro-financing for early-stage bioeconomy startups, targeting bio-based solutions with strong market potential.

- Set up matchmaking platforms to connect SMEs with investors, industrial players, and markets for bio-based products, boosting business visibility and facilitating scale-up.
- Showcase successful bio-based product innovations through pilot projects, demonstrating their commercial viability and societal benefits (e.g., mulching machines and bio-based value-added grape products).
- Strengthen bioeconomy clusters, such as those developed through projects like SCALE-UP, to foster collaboration among businesses, SMEs, research institutions, and local government, enhancing regional competitiveness.
- Promote knowledge exchange on biomass resources and conduct biomass production and compost market assessments. Joint initiatives, such as coordinated biowaste collection for biogas plants, can improve overall biomass utilization.

PILLAR 2: Research and Innovation Capacities and Activities

- Enhance R&D networks by strengthening links between universities, SMEs, and research institutions to build a robust regional R&D ecosystem supporting bioeconomy innovation.
- Establish regular, detailed data collection on bioeconomy and biowaste to inform and strengthen bioeconomy research activities.
- Launch R&I challenges and innovation prizes to stimulate breakthrough solutions that leverage local biomass potential and advance sustainable development goals.
- Encourage publication of research results in high-impact journals to increase regional visibility and attract international collaboration.
- Invest in research on nutrient recycling, focusing on improving compost quality and developing technologies for nutrient extraction and reuse, alongside providing technical support to farmers to reduce reliance on mineral fertilizers.

PILLAR 3: Use of Diverse EU, National, and Regional Funding Streams

- Establish regional “one-stop-shops” to provide SMEs with tailored advice on accessing EU, national, and private funding opportunities for bioeconomy initiatives.
- Provide capacity-building training for SMEs, municipalities, and stakeholders in proposal writing, financial management, and reporting to improve funding success rates.

PILLAR 4: Synergies with Other Policy Fields

- Promote interdepartmental collaboration by establishing working groups involving key local stakeholders (e.g., agriculture, energy, environment) during the development of policy documents such as the LEAP and Waste Management Plan to ensure integrated bioeconomy action.
- Introduce bioeconomy “impact scores” or sustainability indicators to assess and monitor the alignment of new policy proposals with green, circular, and inclusive development goals, ideally within the LEAP.
- Link bioeconomy development with broader regional priorities, such as air quality, climate change, and food systems, to enable a holistic and integrated territorial approach.

- Support local policies promoting composting at both household and industrial levels, complemented by structured waste separation systems and the establishment of demonstration plants to encourage adoption among farmers.

PILLAR 5: Education and Information in Relation to Sustainability

- Integrate bioeconomy modules into primary, secondary, and vocational curricula to raise awareness from an early age and develop a skilled workforce for the bioeconomy sector.
- Expand educational and awareness campaigns targeting farmers, entrepreneurs, youth, and policymakers to deepen understanding of bioeconomy opportunities and sustainability principles.
- Develop tailored professional training programs for technicians, agronomists, and circular economy managers to meet the growing regional demand for bioeconomy skills.
- Use diverse media channels (e.g., newsletters, podcasts, videos, infographics) to promote local bioeconomy successes, highlighting the economic and sustainability impacts of bio-based innovations.
- Maintain the Strumica regional platform as a space for knowledge-sharing, joint planning, and collaborative problem-solving, fostering partnerships among agriculture, public authorities, academia, and civil society.

PILLAR 6: International Collaboration and Sharing Good Practices

- Create formal Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) between Strumica and other bioeconomy regions to ensure sustained cooperation and knowledge-sharing beyond project timelines.
- Promote use of the SCALE-UP platform for sharing regional bioeconomy solutions, best practices, and case studies to support replication and adaptation across regions.
- Organize annual international conferences, rotating among participating countries, to facilitate knowledge exchange with international experts and strengthen long-term collaborations.
- Foster twinning programs, whereby mature bioeconomy regions mentor emerging ones, offering guidance and sharing lessons learned to accelerate development.

General Recommendations (Cross-cutting)

- Define clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure bioeconomy progress at the regional level, preferably integrated into the LEAP as the key local strategic document.
- Ensure active inclusion of women, youth, and marginalized groups in bioeconomy initiatives, leadership roles, and benefit-sharing, enhancing social equity and broadening economic opportunity.
- Improve public communication by shifting from technical project terminology to relatable, community-focused messaging that resonates with local stakeholders.
- Raise broader public awareness of the bioeconomy concept through initiatives such as student competitions in Strumica, which promote creative, bio-based ideas among youth and foster community engagement.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the Strumica Bioeconomy Roadmap demonstrates moderate but meaningful progress across its six pillars, establishing a solid foundation for sustainable growth and alignment with the SDGs. While the initial idea of regional bioeconomy development was introduced through the BE-Rural project, it was the SCALE-UP project that laid the practical groundwork and significantly accelerated on-the-ground activities.

The creation of the Bioeconomy Platform as a first step provided a structured framework for stakeholder engagement and coordination. Building on this, key SCALE-UP activities — such as biopotential mapping, sustainability screening, cluster development, the "Bioeconomy through Art" student competition, and extensive capacity-building and outreach efforts — catalyzed business sector engagement, strengthened research and innovation capacities, and raised public awareness. These efforts contributed notably to advancing SDGs related to economic growth (SDG 8), innovation (SDG 9), responsible consumption (SDG 12), and quality education (SDG 4).

Despite this progress, challenges remain, particularly regarding the pillar on financing flows, which requires stronger mechanisms to mobilize investments and scale up bioeconomy initiatives. The moderate progress observed highlights the importance of sustained investment, coordinated efforts, and continuous stakeholder engagement to fully realize Strumica's potential as a model for regional bioeconomy advancement aligned with national and European sustainability strategies. With continued targeted support, Strumica can evolve from a promising pilot region into a recognized leader of sustainable bioeconomy transformation in Southeast Europe.

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